

IMPORTANCE AND MAIN REQUIREMENTS FOR THE STUDY OF RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AT UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *This article discusses the need to teach future specialists in the field of economics and finance being able to conduct research, search for information, process, analyze and interpret data, the importance of research work of students of higher educational institutions, possible problems of explaining to students the basics of making research in various subjects; describes the purpose of teaching and the topics of the academic discipline "Research Methodology"; presents the requirements for the formation of knowledge, skills, and abilities for the 1st year students after the study of the research basics; concludes with a summary of the importance of teaching research methodology in the higher education.*

Keywords: *science, higher education, research, research work of students, research methodology.*

Improvement of the quality of training in the system of the higher education, the development of science, the development and practical implementation of innovations are becoming increasingly important conditions for ensuring economic growth and achieving the competitiveness of the national economy and improving the welfare of the population [1-2].

Reforms in the higher education system are being carried out in our country, aimed at expanding the improvement of the quality of teaching, the introduction of digital technologies and modern methods in the educational process, and the active involvement of future employers in the process of preparing specialists. Particular attention is paid to improving the effectiveness of research activities in the higher educational institutions, the widespread involvement of young people in scientific activities, and the formation of an innovative science infrastructure [3].

The research work of students is gradually becoming an increasingly significant part of the educational process, necessary for the training of qualified specialists [4-22].

In modern conditions, the ability of future employees of the economic and financial services of enterprises, organizations, ministries, financial managers and financial directors, accountants and auditors, businessmen, individual entrepreneurs, and self-employed persons to be able to make a search, perceive, evaluate and process information, supplement it with missing facts, quickly adapt to new conditions, predict possible changes, plan performance results is of great importance. In the process of teaching various disciplines, it is necessary for the students to develop independence, organization, purposefulness, creative thinking, research skills, skills of critical analysis of available information.

During the performance of research work, the student should learn to conduct research, work with scientific and educational literature, legal documents, analytical reports, statistical collections, systematically read scientific articles, abstracts in collections of scientific conferences, monographs of famous scientists, participate in the discussion of graduation theses and dissertations, analyze the structure and content of scientific papers and articles.

In the process of the implementation of the first independent research works, the student

should receive practical skills and abilities to choose the method of conducting research, ways of processing information, the possibilities of applying scientific knowledge, develops skills in organizing and planning their activities, achieving planned goals and objectives, obtaining research results, their correct interpretation and subsequent registration in accordance with the requirements for each type of scientific work, presentations with the results obtained to a wide audience, holding discussions and defending his or her ideas.

In this regard, it is necessary to solve the following problems:

- How to create a unified basis for students to study research methodology?
- How to determine what basic terms and concepts in the field of research should be known to all students?
 - What methods and means of research should be known to students?
 - How to select the most appropriate methods and tools for conducting various studies in the field of economics and finance?
 - How to tell students about the main stages of the research process?
 - How to teach students to organize their independent research work?
 - How to teach students to work with scientific and educational literature, analytical reports, statistical information, legal documents and other sources?
 - How to teach students to collect, process, analyze and interpret data?
 - How to teach students to put forward their hypotheses, to refute or confirm them?
 - How to explain to students the rules for describing research results?
 - What are the main ways of presenting research results, and how do they differ?
 - What is the best way to explain to students the essence of research ethics and the need to observe it?
 - What information and computer technologies could be used in the process of conducting research or analysis and presenting its results?

To form students with the necessary level of knowledge, skills, and abilities in the field of research from the 2022-2023 academic year, the 1st year students of the Tashkent Institute of Finance study the discipline “Research Methodology”. The purpose of studying the discipline “Research Methodology” is to create the level of knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for the training of highly qualified specialists in the field of scientific research, methodological foundations, structure and main stages of search, collection, and processing of scientific information, as well as organization of theoretical and experimental research, presentation of the research results.

Within the framework of this discipline, the 1st year students should study the following topics:

1. Fundamentals of research.
2. Methodology and methodical basics of research.
3. Tools and methods of research.
4. Stages of the research process.
5. Study of literature and documents.
6. Definition of the research problem.
7. Research project.
8. Collection, processing, and analysis of data.
9. Hypotheses and their verification.

10. Technical description of the study.
11. Research ethics.
12. The role of information technology in research.

At the end of the study of this discipline, students must, students should have an idea, know and be able to use:

- methodological foundations of scientific knowledge;
- search and formulation of a scientific problem;
- essence of research methodology;
- research tools and methods;
- phases and stages of scientific research;
- documentary sources of information necessary for the study;
- procedure for publishing research results;
- final qualifying work and the basics of its writing;
- have practical skills and abilities:
 - to formulate correctly and clearly new scientific problems;
 - to develop research hypotheses and concepts;
 - to properly prepare research materials;
 - to make the right choice of research tools;
 - to draw up a research plan;
 - to search for documentary sources of information;
 - to prepare abstracts of reports and scientific articles;
 - to find complex solutions to problems;
- possess skills in:
 - development of an original concept for solving the problem;
 - determining the priority option for solving the problem;
 - effective use of various methods in the process of conducting research;
 - search for information for research;
 - description of the research results in the form of a scientific work;
 - preparation and publication of abstracts of reports in collections of scientific conferences and scientific articles in peer-reviewed journals;
 - presentations with the results of the research to teachers and other students.

Practical classes use interactive teaching methods that form students' teamwork skills, independent and critical thinking in the profession, a culture of communication and summing up. To conduct practical classes in the discipline “Research Methodology”, interactive methods such as brainstorming, case solving, work in small groups and pairs, the project method and other modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies can be used. Self-study of students is carried out in the form of independent work under the guidance of a teacher and independent work of students.

Thus, research in the higher education becomes a pedagogical action, which provides students with the necessary information about the object of research, the formation of the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities of students to conduct research. The students’ work on this subject includes such processes as defining problems, tasks, assignments, research goals, formulating hypotheses or proposed solutions; collecting, organizing and evaluating data; summarizing and drawing conclusions; and, finally, a thorough check of the conclusions to determine whether they

correspond to the formulated hypothesis, whether they show the achievement of the goal, whether they correspond to the conditions for completing the task. Based on the results of studying the academic discipline “Research Methodology”, students receive the necessary initial knowledge, skills, and abilities in the field of independent conduct of various studies and the presentation of its results.

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